

THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF LANDSCAPE ARCHITECTURE, THEIR APPLICATIONS IN THE COURT ZONES OF THE KHOJA ABDUHOLIK GIZHUVANI ENSEMBLE

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Annotation. *The article studied and analyzed in detail the directions, elements and main provisions of landscape architecture. The implementation of the concept of landscape in Muslim countries has been studied, its types, which are created in the style of a garden that occupies large areas, including ponds and landscaping. The gardens built by the Timurids in the city of Samarkand, approaches and elements inherited from them to our time are analyzed. The landscape design of the Abdukholik Gijduvani complex has been studied. The ancient architectural buildings of the complex, the stone corridors between them and the entrances to the complex, made in the Art Nouveau style, the harmony of front squares, organizational elements of the composition are described.*

Key words: *landscape, landscape architecture, landscape design, area, garden, pond, reservoir interior, landscape.*

Enter. Architecture is an effort to create a spatial environment for human activity can be understood as Creating an open space environment is the main issue of landscape architecture is considered Landscape architecture is the architecture of open spaces, which is external in its organization landscaping and natural relief elements take an important place. In this sense, its unique details as productive of water basins, green spaces, roads, terrain and small architectural details use is a pledge of the optimal solution.

Natural and artificial means of environment and space are a type of creativity in creating a regional landscape is to organize and express. In this case, the open spatial

environment has ecological, functional and aesthetic factors is designed taking into account. For people in human society, it is prosperous and beautiful, lively or quiet, green and creating a bright, comfortable and organized environment has always been a pressing issue and valuable power solved. Of course, the landscape created in front of the building where you live or work is proportional to the building was In this sense, it is a complex of buildings that has become a historical monument for centuries landscape created in front of multi-storey buildings (residence, public building). fundamentally different in content and content [1,2,3].

Bukhara is an open-air museum, center of religious and worldly knowledge, Islamic culture recognized as There are a lot of structures included in the UNESCO list in the territory of Bukhara region. Hazrat Khwaja Abdulkhaliq Gijduvani - Khojayi, who left a name in Islam with Sufism Jahon (1103 - 1179), Hazrat Khoja Arif Revhari - Mohitoban (1166 - 1263), Hazrat Khoja Mahmud Anjirfagnavi (died - 1286), Hazrat Khoja Ali Rometani - Khojayi Azizon (1191 - 1321), . Hazrat Khoja Muhammad Babayi Samosi (q. s.) (died - 1335), Hazrat Khoja Sayyid Amir Kulol (1281 - 1370), the tombs of Hazrat Khoja Bahauddin Naqshband Bukhari (1318 - 1389) today they have become big shrines. In front of these ensembles that tell stories from the distant past organized landscape, what principles, requirements and rules of landscaping are in accordance with the territory. It is not without benefits to learn what to pay attention to in order to be beautiful and prosperous.

Theoretical basis. Landscape architecture has changed its spatial dimensions over time relying on standing living things, accepting and perceiving it is precisely the movement of objects It is unique as it has a complex effect on human senses appears as a whole spatial composition with characteristics. Environment landscaping, landscape art developed along with human civilization, development of society, humanity reflected lifestyle trends. It was even created around buildings in ancient times greenery, compositional solutions, gardens are seen as an element and symbol of paradise on earth, he was treated with respect. Omar Khayyam told me that heaven is the highest reward. There are fairies there is charm, the sweetness of grapes. But what would heaven be for me, I'm still from the garden I have everything without going out. The entry of gardens into Islamic culture dates back to the 6th century will come. Before that, they used meadows and hills instead of gardens. Around residential houses there were almost no large green areas.

Every householder had a farm, which was used for farming there were rest corners. Charbogs have existed as a style of landscape architecture and design for a long time. The word Чопбор seems to be a concept specific to the ancient Muslim nation, the Uzbeks. In such areas trees and shrubs with branched upper part, lawns with widespread wild plants will be. The main attention is paid to the natural landscape,

even artificial water bodies they are organized as if they were created by nature itself. Lives in the area of classic swamps (green) walls are created, sheds are built, sheds are installed [4,5,6,7]. The plan of the traditional gardens of Muslim countries is the city-garden and paradise of Persia created using a mixture of gardens (interpreted in the Qur'an and hadiths). The luxurious decoration of Muslim gardens, the presence of rare plants, birds and animals it is explained by the fact that green areas are always located mainly in countries with a subtropical climate. Islamic gardens are in conditions of careful treatment of the animal world and water formed.

The whole world knows that Great Amir Temur built huge structures, but Samarkand many people do not know how he made his city green. Beautiful gardens surround summer palaces created. Such beautification works, methods of greening the areas have passed centuries and are today are methods that have reached today and have become traditions. Of course, such gardens have survived to this day did not come, but archaeological findings about their structural structure, medieval miniatures, etc can be found out through correspondence. In the center of such gardens was the ruler's palace (in some cases, a shed) and an avenue leading to it from four sides.

The gardens were full of fruit and non-fruit, decorative trees, flowers and greenery. They are placed in a certain order, at the same interval. The gardens are guarded and there are pheasants and storks flying, deer leaping, fountains abounding, leading to and from there are many trees with receding tributaries, hiding pools with their branches was When there is no ruler, representatives of art and culture gather in the garden, they enjoyed the environment and created. Gardens with romantic or descriptive names named "Garden Wind", "Garden Dilkusho", "Garden Beshikht", "Garden Chinor", "Garden Nau", "Garden miniatures about gardens such as "Baland", Davlatabad Garden", "Maydan Garden", "Dzhakhonnamo Garden drawn, written down in works. Built in 1378-1404 and recognized by the world as luxury Gardens of Amir Temur have not reached today. Their names refer to the regions where they are located moved and preserved until today. Bogishamol and Bogi-Zagon residents of Samarkand city residential areas are among them [8,9,10]. In Central Asia, traditional gardens are established in front of their houses, in the inner courtyard it has become a habit even for the households of poor families. In the shade of trees, on a bench each of the old people drinking green tea and enjoying the green surroundings, in the created flower gardens can be seen in front of the gate.

a)

b)

Figure 1. Examples from the Timurids in Samarkand (a) and Guzar gardens in Bukhara (b).(miniature of Nafisa Gilmanova).

There are two types of gardens: sorbog - a geometric rectangular shape, each of its side is about 1 km long. Ditches (water streams) passed through their territory in four directions. Four towers were built in the corner, a palace and a shed were built in the middle. The gates were built on the side of the city. The second type of gardens includes contour gardens that do not have a precise geometric shape. Such fountains, ditches, avenues around them were designed in some corner of the gardens. Such the gardens had a wide nomenclature of plants, trees and fauna.

Results: 200-220 years after the death of Abdulkholiq Gijduvani, Mirzo Ulugbek built a madrasa in front of his grave. Then the grave Surobi is covered with marble slabs, called "dakhma" and in the direction transverse to the madrasa has. A "hazira" has been built around the shack, where it is possible to visit it while walking around. The surroundings are beautified and landscaped. Later, the Khazira was demolished, and the area is deserted has come to the situation. In 2003, Khoja Abdulkhaliq Gijduvani, a major representative of Sufism in Bukhara The 900th anniversary of his birth was held at a high organizational level with the participation of UNESCO [1, 14, 16, 17, 18,19, 20]. His mausoleum complex was built in Gijduvan. A new mosque is also part of this complex there is The madrasa of Mirzo Ulugbek near the mausoleum was repaired (photo 1).

Figure 1. Historical (in a-miniature) of the Abdukholiq Gijduvani ensemble and re-released in 2003 condition after construction (b).

Figure 2. The condition of the Abdukholiq Gijduvani complex after 2018.

The entire complex covers an area of 4 ha. Front area of the complex, side plots beautified, sidewalks were paved, flower beds, trees and green spaces were created. In general landscape design was performed based on certain laws. Organized landscape regular It is characteristic of the arranged landscape direction. The terrain of the square is architecturally designed and the main buildings it has been achieved to show them in full, ensuring that they are superior and high compared to others. Reorganization of the water basin (pond) with a clear contour and shape, around it, smooth contoured paths on the field, standing trees and bushes in clear rows can be observed. These are organized and beautified by human power. Historical The part where the buildings are

located and the front area, decorated in a modern color, provide a successful combination of charm, beauty and architectural compactness and precision in the whole composition. The difference between them, the transition from one to the other is not felt at all [11,12,13].

The chosen style is an opportunity to show the noble beauty and wealth of nature has This style of landscape has a sense of norm, a well-thought-out structure and some predictability non-existent edges (features) are characteristic. All elements of such a landscape at a glance it is impossible to understand, to feel, they are gradually understood. Very thorough on all details is processed. The modernity of the style can be seen in the simplicity and strict shape of the plots is standing. It is also an elegant and beautiful decorative element that fulfills a practical functional task used. Flower garden, corridor, greenery, hydrotechnical facilities - water supply facilities the correct geometric shape is given. Plots are flat green areas, modern engineering systems, including automatic irrigation systems, "smart light" system, etc. From the bushes it is possible to observe the green fenced walls, flowers are placed in the fields.

Summary. An important part of landscape design is learning styles and always in the community of people the planning solution of the site where the building is located with the architecture of the building and the environment surrounding it solved in harmony. The landscape design of the Abdukhaliq Gijduvani complex is in a modern style done. The organization of a flat relief area, in which there are clearly shaped, contoured greens, paths The completion of hydrotechnical structures is its proof.

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